

Original Research

Analysis of Diversification Strategies and Organizational Performance of Private Information Technology Companies in Kenya

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of diversification strategies on the performance of private IT companies in Kenya, with government ICT policy included as a moderating variable. The objectives were to evaluate the influence of concentric diversification on company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya, analyze the influence of conglomerate diversification (Mergers, Acquisitions and Joint Ventures) on company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya and to find out the moderating influence of Government IT Sector Policy on the relationship between diversification strategy and company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya. The study was mainly anchored on Resource-Based Theory, Dynamic Capabilities Theory, and Balanced Scorecard Theory. A descriptive research design was employed. The population comprised 433 registered private IT firms, from which a simple random sample of 208 companies was drawn. Out of the targeted 208 respondents, 175 returned completed questionnaires, yielding a response rate of 84%. Data was collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed through descriptive statistics, correlation, and multiple regression analyses using SPSS. The findings indicate that concentric and conglomerate diversification strategies positively and significantly influence company performance. However, the moderating effect of government ICT policy on this relationship was weak and statistically insignificant. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.774, showing that 77.4% of the variance in performance could be explained by the diversification strategies applied. The study concludes that internal diversification strategies play a more critical role in driving performance than external policy factors. It recommends that private IT firms strategically invest in diversification and innovation to enhance competitiveness and sustain growth.

Keywords: Diversification, Government ICT policy, Performance.

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Introduction

Diversification strategy is a key driver of firm performance, aimed at reducing risk and enhancing profitability by expanding into new products, services, or markets. It is commonly classified into concentric, horizontal, vertical, and conglomerate forms, depending on the degree of relatedness to a firm's existing operations (Thirathon & Meeprom, 2020). Effective diversification enables firms to leverage existing capabilities, access new revenue sources, and build resilience against market shocks (Burak, 2018). For ICT firms, diversification may involve expanding into areas such as software development, cloud computing, cybersecurity, or managed digital services. When aligned with internal capabilities and market opportunities, diversification improves financial outcomes, market share, and strategic positioning (Kim, 2021). Global ICT leaders such as Google, Amazon, and Microsoft exemplify how strategic diversification enhances sustained performance through multiple revenue streams, economies of scale, and innovation capacity (Teece, 2018). Similarly, African firms like Safaricom and MTN have diversified into mobile money, health, and education platforms, resulting in increased revenue and market penetration (GSMA, 2023). However, many African ICT firms, including those in Kenya, face constraints such as limited capital, skill shortages, and inadequate institutional support, which restrict diversification and strategic expansion (UNCTAD, 2021). Kenyan private ICT firms largely operate in lower market segments, focusing on basic digital services and hardware resale, with minimal participation in higher-value activities or regional markets.

Although previous research has explored diversification and performance globally and regionally, limited empirical evidence exists on how diversification influences the performance of private ICT firms in Kenya, particularly when considering the moderating role of government ICT policy. Government regulations, incentives, and sectoral frameworks directly affect resource allocation, innovation, and competitiveness, thereby influencing the strength of the diversification–performance relationship (MoICT, 2022). This gap is significant given the ICT sector's contribution to Kenya's Vision 2030 agenda and its role in national economic transformation (KNBS, 2019). The present study therefore examines how concentric and conglomerate diversification strategies affect the organisational performance of private ICT firms in Kenya, while assessing the moderating effect of government ICT policy. By addressing this empirical gap, the study provides evidence-based insights to support managerial decision-making and inform policy interventions aimed at enhancing the growth and competitiveness of Kenya's ICT industry.

Statement of Problem

The information and communication technology (ICT) sector plays a central role in driving innovation, productivity, and competitiveness across modern economies. In Kenya, private ICT firms contribute significantly to digital transformation and service delivery, yet their long-term sustainability depends on effective strategic management practices. One such strategy is diversification, which enables firms to expand into new markets or products to enhance performance and reduce operational risk. Although global research has widely demonstrated that diversification improves organisational outcomes, empirical evidence from Kenya's private ICT sector remains limited. Most existing

studies have concentrated on public-sector ICT initiatives, innovation frameworks, or broad business strategies, leaving the dynamics of private firms underexplored (Wario & Khalfan, 2021).

Even where performance has been investigated, diversification has rarely been isolated as a distinct factor, resulting in insufficient understanding of how concentric and conglomerate strategies influence market share, customer satisfaction, revenue growth, and operational efficiency (Mungai & Mwangi, 2022). Evidence from other industries supports the positive contribution of diversification to firm performance. For example, Wambui and Kavale (2022) found that diversification strategies accounted for 45.6% of performance variation among insurance firms, with concentric diversification ($\beta = 0.252$, $p < .05$) and conglomerate diversification ($\beta = 0.199$, $p < .05$) both exerting significant positive effects. Similarly, Achayo, Melly, and Mwanza (2023) reported that portfolio diversification explained 72.1% of the variance in financial performance among large enterprises in Kisumu County ($R^2 = .721$, $p < .05$). However, none of these studies have examined Kenya's private ICT sector, where rapid technological change, market volatility, and competition from multinational corporations create unique strategic challenges (Mulupi, 2022).

Furthermore, the moderating role of government ICT policy on firm performance remains underexplored. Although national ICT policies aim to foster innovation, digital transformation, and sustainable sectoral growth (MoICT, 2022), there is little empirical evidence on their influence on private firms' strategic decisions and outcomes. The extent to which alignment between diversification strategies and government ICT regulations strengthens or limits performance is still unclear. Addressing this gap is essential to understanding how internal diversification strategies interact with external policy environments to shape organisational performance. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the effect of diversification strategies on the performance of private ICT firms in Kenya, while assessing the moderating influence of government ICT policy. The findings will provide context-specific insights to guide managers and policymakers in enhancing competitiveness and achieving sustainable growth within the ICT sector.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to analyze the effect of diversification strategies on company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya.

The specific objectives of the Study were;

- i. To evaluate the influence of concentric diversification on company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya.
- ii. To analyze the influence of conglomerate diversification (Mergers, Acquisitions and Joint Ventures) on company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya.
- iii. To find out the moderating influence of Government IT Sector Policy on the relationship between diversification strategy and company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 to assess the significance level of confidence that guided the study;

H₁: There is no statistically significant influence between concentric diversification and company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya.

H₂: There is no statistically significant influence between conglomerate diversification (Mergers, Acquisitions and Joint Ventures) and company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya.

H₃: There is no statistically significant moderating effect of government IT sector policy did not have a statistically significant moderating effect on the relationship between diversification strategy and company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya.

Theoretical Review

Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

The Resource-Based View theory was introduced by Wernerfelt in 1984 and later refined by Barney in 1991. This theory explains how organizations gain a competitive edge by controlling strategic internal resources. These resources must be valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable to provide sustained competitive advantage. RBV links performance to assets that firms own, such as innovation capacity, infrastructure, and human talent. Shahmansouri et al. (2019) explain that organizations succeed when they utilize both tangible and intangible resources. Cardeal and António (2021) further stress that unless firms have the skills to use their resources, those resources remain unproductive. Lugasi and Kariuki (2018) found that firms with strategic assets perform better in competitive environments. The theory is relevant to this study as it explains how private ICT companies in Kenya use their internal resources to support diversification strategies.

RBV theory faces several criticisms despite its wide use. One major limitation is the challenge in identifying and measuring high-value strategic resources objectively. According to Enriquez (2019), the theory lacks practical tools for assessing which resources provide a true advantage. Kraaijenbrink et al. (2018) argue that RBV does not offer guidance on how firms should develop or transform their resources. Another critique is that RBV assumes a stable environment which limits its application in fast-changing sectors like ICT. The theory also downplays the role of external influences such as market dynamics or policy changes. This static view weakens its usefulness in explaining performance in volatile industries. These criticisms provide the rationale for considering complementary theories like Dynamic Capabilities. RBV theory is directly applicable to the current study. The theory helps explain how private ICT companies in Kenya pursue diversification based on the resources they possess. The study used RBV to assess how firms apply their innovation, skilled personnel, and infrastructure to gain a competitive edge.

Dynamic Capabilities Theory

Dynamic Capabilities theory was developed by Teece, Pisano and Shuen in 1997 as an evolution of the RBV theory. It addresses RBV's limitations by focusing on how firms adapt and renew resources in changing environments. The theory introduces three main functions which include sensing, seizing and transforming. These functions help organizations remain competitive by continuously aligning their strategies with market demands. According to Teece (2018), firms that respond quickly to environmental changes perform better. Girod and Whittington (2017) argue that dynamic capabilities are essential in industries affected by rapid innovation. The ICT sector in Kenya is highly dynamic and therefore requires firms to reconfigure resources frequently. This makes the theory relevant to the study.

Despite its strengths, the theory has faced criticism for being vague and hard to apply in practice. Yi, Han and Cha (2018) point out that there is no clear agreement on what qualifies as a dynamic capability. The lack of clarity makes it difficult for researchers to measure the theory's constructs accurately. Another criticism is that simply having dynamic capabilities does not guarantee improved performance. According to Suddaby et al. (2020), firms must deploy these capabilities in a targeted way to see benefits. The theory also does not specify how firms can develop such capabilities. This creates challenges when applying the theory in empirical research. These weaknesses must be addressed for the theory to provide practical value.

The theory was used in this study to explain how private ICT firms in Kenya adapt their strategies in response to market shifts. Dynamic capabilities help explain how these firms manage resource renewal when implementing diversification. According to Ko and Liu (2017), firms with stronger dynamic capabilities are better at using their assets to pursue new opportunities. The study considered how firms sense opportunities and adjust their internal operations. This theory also informed the investigation of how environmental factors, such as government policy, affect firm decisions. Dynamic capabilities theory was thus vital in linking policy influence to strategic diversification. It added depth to the analysis of how firms respond to changing sector conditions. The theory complemented RBV by focusing on resource flexibility and adaptation.

Balanced Scorecard (BSC) Theory

Balanced Scorecard theory was developed by Kaplan and Norton in 1992 to align business activities with strategic goals. It measures performance through four perspectives which include financial, customer, internal processes and learning and growth. The approach provides a comprehensive view of performance beyond just financial indicators. Sirait (2018) highlights that BSC focuses on increasing earnings, improving productivity and gaining market share. Oliveira et al. (2021) argue that the BSC is effective because it balances both tangible and intangible performance indicators. The theory is widely used in sectors where customer satisfaction and innovation are critical. Dimitropoulos et al. (2017) note that BSC helps link daily operations to long-term strategy. This makes the theory suitable for evaluating performance in private ICT firms.

One critique of the BSC is that it can be inflexible in volatile environments. Korenková, Závadský and Lis (2019) argue that the selection of indicators is often subjective and lacks standardization. The theory also requires regular updates to remain aligned with company changes. Another challenge is the difficulty of measuring intangible elements such as employee growth or learning. These limitations can reduce the accuracy of the performance measurement process. The BSC also assumes that all strategic goals can be quantified which is not always practical. The theory must be adapted to fit dynamic industries like ICT. Despite these weaknesses, BSC remains useful for structured performance evaluation. Table 1 below shows how the three models compliment each other to provide a solid theoretical backing of the study.

Table 1: Linkage of Theories

Theoretical Focus	Main Contribution	Linkage to Others
RBV Theory	Identifies strategic internal resources that drive performance.	Provides the foundation of competitive advantage upon which DC and BSC build.
Dynamic Capabilities Theory	Explains how firms adapt and renew resources in changing environments.	Extends RBV by introducing flexibility and connects with BSC through the operationalisation of adaptability.
Balanced Scorecard Theory	Measures and is consistent resource use and strategic activities with performance outcomes.	Translates both RBV and DC concepts into measurable results and feedback loops.

Source: (Barney, 1991; Teece, Pisano and Shuen, 1997; Kaplan and Norton in 1992)

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. Conceptual framework

Empirical Review

Diversification as a corporate strategy has been widely investigated for its impact on firm performance across different industries and contexts. Empirical studies indicate that concentric diversification, which involves expansion into related products or services, enhances profitability, competitive advantage, and firm growth. For example, Rishi, Rudra, and Vinay (2014) demonstrated that non-financial firms in India benefited from improved corporate size, asset tangibility, and operational performance following the adoption of concentric diversification. Similarly, conglomerate diversification, which includes mergers, acquisitions, and joint ventures, has been shown to improve market share, return on investment, and operational efficiency (Bhatia & Thakur, 2018). Collectively, these findings suggest that diversification strategies create synergies, optimize resource utilisation, and expand market reach. However, most studies have focused on non-African contexts, limiting their applicability to Kenyan ICT firms, which face unique regulatory, technological, and market challenges.

In Kenya, research on ICT firms has largely focused on general strategic planning and growth determinants rather than on diversification strategies per se. Awino (2019) found that structured strategic planning in ICT SMEs contributed to competitive advantage and market positioning, while Ikua and Namusonge (2019) highlighted innovation, technology adoption, and managerial capability as drivers of growth in Nairobi-based ICT firms. While these studies underscore the importance of strategic approaches, they do not examine the specific impacts of concentric and conglomerate diversification on firm performance. Moreover, the potential moderating role of government ICT policy, which can influence resource allocation, market access, and operational outcomes, has received little empirical attention. This represents a critical gap, given the policy-driven nature of the Kenyan ICT sector and the potential for regulation to either enable or constrain strategic initiatives.

The foregoing review indicates a clear empirical gap regarding the relationship between diversification strategies and company performance in the Kenyan private ICT sector. Existing studies either focus on different industries, are situated in non-African contexts, or address strategic planning without isolating the effects of concentric versus conglomerate diversification. Furthermore, the moderating influence of government ICT policy remains largely unexplored, despite its likely role in shaping the effectiveness of strategic decisions. This gap necessitates the present study, which seeks to provide robust empirical evidence on how concentric and conglomerate diversification strategies affect performance in private ICT firms and to determine whether government ICT policy moderates these relationships, thereby contributing to a more nuanced understanding of strategic management in the Kenyan ICT sector.

Research Methodology

The study was guided by the positivism research philosophy, which asserts that observable and measurable phenomena can generate reliable and generalizable knowledge (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). This approach was appropriate as it enabled the researcher to quantify and analyse the relationships between diversification strategies and company performance, providing an objective basis for drawing conclusions. The study adopted a descriptive research design, suitable for examining variables in their natural settings and for collecting detailed information on the characteristics of the defined population (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The target population consisted of 433 private information technology companies registered with the ICT Authority of Kenya, with inclusion restricted to firms operational for more than three years to ensure availability of reliable performance data. Using the Yamane formula (1967), a sample of 208 firms was drawn, of which 175 responded, representing a response rate of 84%. Simple random sampling was employed to select firms that were most active and prominent in terms of size and market presence, ensuring that the data captured firms most relevant to studying the effects of diversification strategies.

The study adopted a simple random sampling technique to ensure proportional representation of employees across different departments in private ICT firms. The sample size was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula, which assumes random sampling. Stratification allowed the researcher to capture variations among managerial and operational levels while maintaining the random selection principle within each stratum. This approach ensured sampling consistency and addressed earlier methodological concerns about potential bias associated with purposive sampling. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire designed to capture respondents' views on the study variables. The instrument consisted of closed-ended questions based on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from *1 = Strongly Disagree* to *5 = Strongly Agree*. The questionnaire was divided into five key sections: demographic data, concentric diversification (X_1), conglomerate diversification (X_2), government ICT policy (X_3), and organisational performance (Y). Each construct was measured using multiple indicators derived from existing validated studies and tailored to fit the Kenyan ICT industry context.

The operationalisation of variables is shown in Table 2. It details how each construct was measured, the type of scale used, and the expected relationship with performance outcomes.

Table 2. Variable Operationalisation Matrix

Variable	Indicators	Scale	Expected Outcome	Source
Concentric Diversification (X ₁)	Product relatedness, market synergy, resource sharing	Likert (1–5)	Positive	Adapted from Rumelt (1982)
Conglomerate Diversification (X ₂)	Mergers and acquisitions, unrelated ventures, financial spread	Likert (1–5)	Positive	Adapted from Grant (2019)
Government ICT Policy (X ₃)	Regulatory framework, infrastructure support, policy incentives	Likert (1–5)	Moderating	Adapted from GoK (2021)
Organisational Performance (Y)	Financial performance, customer satisfaction, innovation, learning and growth	Likert (1–5)	Dependent	Adapted from Kaplan & Norton (1992)

To ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted among 20 respondents drawn from ICT firms not included in the main sample. The pilot aimed to test the clarity, relevance, and structure of the questionnaire. Content validity was examined using the Content Validity Index (CVI), where experts in ICT management and research methods rated each item for relevance and clarity. Items rated as relevant (3 or 4 on a four-point scale) were used to compute the CVI. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Content Validity Index Results

Variable	Number of Items	CVI Value	Interpretation
Concentric Diversification (X ₁)	6	0.89	Acceptable
Conglomerate Diversification (X ₂)	6	0.86	Acceptable
Government ICT Policy (X ₃)	5	0.91	Excellent
Organisational Performance (Y)	7	0.93	Excellent

All CVI values were above 0.8, the minimum acceptable threshold, confirming strong content validity (Polit & Beck, 2021). This indicated that the questionnaire effectively represented the study’s constructs. Reliability was then tested using Cronbach’s Alpha, which measures the internal consistency of the items. According to Taber (2018), a value of 0.7 or higher demonstrates acceptable reliability. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Results

Variable	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha (α)	Interpretation
Concentric Diversification (X_1)	6	0.84	Reliable
Conglomerate Diversification (X_2)	6	0.88	Reliable
Government ICT Policy (X_3)	5	0.82	Reliable
Organisational Performance (Y)	7	0.90	Highly Reliable

All constructs recorded alpha values above the 0.7 threshold, confirming that the instrument was internally consistent and dependable for data collection. Before regression analysis, diagnostic tests were carried out to verify that the data met the assumptions of classical linear regression. The Shapiro–Wilk test and Q–Q plots confirmed that residuals followed a normal distribution ($p > .05$). Multicollinearity tests showed that all Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values were between 1.12 and 2.08, indicating no multicollinearity issues. A correlation matrix confirmed that the relationships among the independent variables were linear and within acceptable limits. Residual plots were used to check for homoscedasticity, confirming that the variance of errors remained constant across fitted values. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were applied to summarise the data and construct composite indices for each variable. Multiple regression analysis was then conducted to assess the effects of concentric and conglomerate diversification on organisational performance, as well as the moderating influence of government ICT policy. To test the relationships between variables, multiple linear regression analysis was applied using the model:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \varepsilon$$

Where;

Y = company performance

β_0 = Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression coefficients

X_1 = Concentric diversification

X_2 = Conglomerate diversification

X_3 = Government ICT policy

ε = Error term

Research Findings

Concentric Diversification

The study determined how concentric diversification influenced the performance of private information technology companies in Nairobi County by asking respondents the extent to which they agreed or disagreed the statements on concentric diversification.

Table 5. Concentric Diversification on company Performance

Statement on Concentric Diversification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Reached Wider Audience	175	1.663	0.474
Make New Products	175	1.509	0.501
Acquire Viable Business Synergy	175	2.349	0.952
Increased Market Share	175	1.160	0.368
Improved Marketing	175	1.491	0.501
Enhanced Production Capacity	175	2.171	0.682
Enhanced Strategic Advantage	175	1.491	0.501

The analysis of concentric diversification shows that private ICT firms in Kenya are drawing several benefits from adopting this strategy. The results demonstrate that diversification is increasing market share ($M = 1.160$, $SD = 0.368$), supporting earlier findings by Oladimeji and Udosen (2019), who argue that diversification strategies enable firms to capture new customer segments and defend their market position. Respondents also indicated that diversification helps organizations reach wider audiences ($M = 1.663$, $SD = 0.474$), which is consistent with the arguments of Yi, Han, and Cha (2018) that small and medium enterprises benefit from leveraging diversification to expand their technical and market performance. Improved marketing ($M = 1.491$, $SD = 0.501$) and enhanced strategic advantage ($M = 1.491$, $SD = 0.501$) were also emphasised, reflecting Teece's (2018) dynamic capabilities theory, which posits that firms strengthen their long-term competitiveness by strategically aligning and reconfiguring resources. Moreover, diversification through product development ($M = 1.509$, $SD = 0.501$) echoes findings by Rishi, Rudra, and Vinay (2014), who highlight that related diversification fosters innovation and improves profitability by broadening a firm's scope of offerings.

However, the study also shows that concentric diversification is yielding moderate results in enhancing production capacity ($M = 2.171$, $SD = 0.682$) and acquiring viable business synergy ($M = 2.349$, $SD = 0.952$). This finding resonates with Koryak et al. (2015), who caution that diversification strategies often face implementation challenges when firms lack sufficient managerial or financial resources to realise full synergy. Similarly, Montgomery, Peck, and Vining (2021) emphasise that expansion into related products requires careful alignment of capacity, systems, and processes to avoid operational inefficiencies. Taken together, the overall mean score across the items is 1.833, which indicates that concentric diversification is generally perceived positively by

respondents, though its success is stronger in marketing and market expansion outcomes than in achieving synergy and production efficiencies. These findings support the resource-based view (Barney, 1991) by illustrating that diversification allows firms to redeploy existing resources into related markets for competitive advantage, while also highlighting the importance of developing dynamic capabilities to overcome operational constraints.

Conglomerate Diversification

The study sought to determine the effect of conglomerate diversification on the performance of private information technology companies in Kenya. The findings are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Conglomerate Diversification on company Performance

Statement on Conglomerate Diversification	n	Mean	Std. Deviation
Market Share	175	2.000	-
Growth In Asset Base	175	2.491	0.501
Increased Customer Satisfaction	175	2.000	0.816
Improved Productivity and ROI	175	1.989	0.577
Gained Competitive Advantage	175	2.149	0.687

The study results indicate that conglomerate diversification is playing an important role in improving the performance of private ICT firms in Kenya. Respondents noted that this strategy enhances productivity and return on investment ($M = 1.989$, $SD = 0.577$), showing that combining resources through mergers, acquisitions, or joint ventures is helping firms use capital more effectively. These outcomes are in line with Bhatia and Thakur (2018), who observed that diversification strategies contribute positively to financial performance by reducing risk and broadening operational opportunities. The findings further suggest that firms adopting conglomerate diversification are experiencing improvements in customer satisfaction ($M = 2.000$, $SD = 0.816$) and market share ($M = 2.000$). This observation supports Thirathon and Meeprom (2020), who emphasised that diversification strategies allow firms to appeal to wider customer bases, thereby strengthening their market reach and competitiveness.

The results also show that conglomerate diversification is associated with growth in the asset base ($M = 2.491$, $SD = 0.501$) and a stronger competitive position ($M = 2.149$, $SD = 0.687$). This is consistent with the resource-based view, which holds that firms gain advantage when they acquire rare and valuable resources through strategic diversification (Barney, 1991). In addition, Ko and Liu (2017) argue that such diversification enhances the dynamic capabilities of firms, enabling them to adapt to changing markets while making better use of their resources. Nonetheless, the relatively higher mean score for asset base compared to other indicators suggests that firms are accumulating assets faster than they are translating them into improved operational efficiency, pointing to the need for better integration. The overall mean score of 2.126 across all the items suggests that

conglomerate diversification is having a generally positive effect on performance, reinforcing earlier evidence by Oladimeji and Udosen (2019) that well-structured diversification strategies strengthen company competitiveness and long-term growth.

Mergers and Acquisitions

The study sought to establish the effect of mergers and acquisitions as a diversification strategy on the performance of private information technology companies in Kenya. The findings are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Mergers

Statement on Mergers	n	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pricing leader	175	1.840	.3676
Gained Competitive Advantage	175	2.160	.3677
Increased Market Share and Asset Base	175	1.669	.4721
Gained Managerial Experience	175	2.000	.5870
Increased Brand Visibility	175	2.160	.6928

The findings reveal that the majority of respondents agreed that mergers and acquisitions led to an increase in market share and asset base, reflected by a mean of 1.669 and a standard deviation of 0.472. This outcome is consistent with Gaughan (2022), who notes that mergers and acquisitions strengthen financial capacity and market positioning by enabling firms to consolidate resources and expand their operational scale. Respondents also indicated that firms gained managerial expertise through these strategies, with a mean of 2.0, a finding that resonates with the resource-based view (Barney, 1991), which underscores the importance of acquiring new knowledge, skills, and capabilities in driving competitive advantage. The study further established that firms benefited from synergy, including becoming price leaders, with a mean of 1.84. Additionally, respondents agreed that these diversification strategies enhanced competitive advantage, with a mean of 2.16 and a standard deviation of 0.368. This is consistent with the work of Boateng and Bi (2022), who found that mergers and acquisitions are vital for firms seeking to sustain competitiveness in dynamic and globalized markets. Overall, the findings suggest that mergers and acquisitions contribute not only to asset and market growth but also to managerial capability, synergy, and stronger competitive positioning, which reflects the broader theoretical and empirical perspectives on corporate diversification strategies.

Joint Ventures

The study sought to establish the effect of joint ventures as a diversification strategy to beat the effects. The study theorized that organizations needed to survive the effect of the adverse measures undertaken by the government.

Table 8. Joint Ventures and company Performance

Statement on Joint Ventures	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Overcame Market Entry Challenges	175	1.663	0.474
Acquired Valuable Human Resource Skills	175	1.834	0.373
Increased Market Share and Asset Base	175	1.712	0.462
Gained Managerial Experience	175	1.947	0.528
Reduced Cost of Doing Business	175	1.589	0.497

The results show that respondents viewed joint ventures as highly beneficial for company growth and competitiveness. One of the strongest outcomes was the role of joint ventures in overcoming entry barriers into new markets ($M = 1.663$, $SD = 0.474$). This resonates with the work of Gaur and Lu (2022), who observed that joint ventures give firms access to host-country partners' knowledge, networks, and institutional legitimacy, enabling smoother entry into foreign or unfamiliar markets. Respondents also highlighted that joint ventures enabled firms to acquire valuable human resource skills ($M = 1.834$, $SD = 0.373$). This is consistent with Kim et al., (2024), who found that collaborations through joint ventures facilitate the transfer of managerial expertise and technical know-how, which are crucial intangible assets for company development. The literature further emphasises that such skill acquisition enhances firm-level innovation and performance, especially in competitive industries like ICT, where talent and knowledge are critical drivers of success.

In addition, the findings indicated that joint ventures helped firms increase market share and asset base ($M = 1.712$, $SD = 0.462$), gain managerial experience ($M = 1.947$, $SD = 0.528$), and reduce the cost of doing business ($M = 1.589$, $SD = 0.497$). Bhatia and Thakur (2018) similarly noted that firms engaging in joint ventures often achieve economies of scale, operational efficiency, and competitive advantage through shared resources and infrastructure. These findings are also supported by Luo and Tung (2018), who explained that joint ventures promote company learning, enhance resource utilisation, and build capabilities that drive long-term growth. Overall, the average mean (≈ 1.749) shows that respondents largely agreed on the positive contribution of joint ventures to performance. The evidence therefore strengthens existing scholarship by demonstrating that, within the Kenyan ICT sector, joint ventures are not only reducing costs and improving efficiency but also contributing significantly to market growth, capability building, and sustainable performance.

Government IT Sector Policy

The study sought to measure the effect of government IT Sector Policy as a moderating factor between diversification strategies adopted by private information technology companies and their company performance. The study hypothesized that diversified private information technology companies were likely to perform better if the government provided an enabling environment for doing business. The government IT sector policy is aimed to provide a level playing field for all players in the information technology sector and to ensure that IT companies conduct business without any legal impediments.

This study viewed government intervention in three aspects; training, Innovation and Support.

Skills Acquisition

The study analyzed the effect of aligning a firm's training or skills acquisition policy to the government policy.

Table 9. Skills Acquisition

Statement on Skills Acquisition	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Leverage on Govt IT sector policy	175	2.0114	0.57724
Aligned Operations to Govt IT Sector Policy	175	1.6743	0.46999
Aligned Staff actions to IT sector policy	175	1.8171	0.68711
Consistency in service delivery	175	1.4857	0.50123
Retention and motivating Valuable Human Resources	175	2.0000	0.58722
Skills and Joint venture acquisitions aligned to IT Sector Policy	175	3.1714	0.89974

The results in Table 9 indicate that integrating government ICT policy with company talent management practices is shaping key aspects of firm performance. Consistency in service delivery recorded the strongest effect ($M = 1.486$, $SD = 0.501$), showing that aligning skills acquisition and retention strategies with national policy frameworks is improving operational reliability. This finding corresponds with Owino and Kwasira (2022), who emphasized that coherence between regulatory policies and internal practices enhances efficiency in ICT firms by minimizing duplication and ensuring service quality. Similarly, aligning company operations to government IT policies ($M = 1.674$, $SD = 0.470$) and staff actions to the same framework ($M = 1.817$, $SD = 0.687$) reflects recognition that policy consistency strengthens accountability and structured decision-making. These insights are supported by Muriithi and Awino (2021), who found that policy alignment in ICT enterprises boosts institutional compliance and mitigates operational risks, thereby contributing positively to company performance.

The findings further show that leveraging government ICT policy plays an important role in retaining and motivating valuable human resources ($M = 2.000$, $SD = 0.587$), underlining the role of policy-driven HR strategies in sustaining employee commitment. This is consistent with Akinwale and George (2022), who observed that government-backed ICT frameworks create enabling conditions that enhance employee morale and professional development. By contrast, the relatively higher mean for aligning skills and joint venture acquisitions with IT sector policy ($M = 3.171$, $SD = 0.900$) suggests weaker or inconsistent outcomes. This points to a limited connection between external policy frameworks and the internal integration of skills through joint ventures, potentially arising from bureaucratic barriers or misaligned priorities between firms and regulators. The overall mean score (≈ 1.97) reflects a general consensus that linking skills acquisition strategies to government ICT policy contributes positively to performance, though the mixed responses imply that benefits are uneven. These results correspond with

contemporary scholarship highlighting that policy alignment is most effective when combined with company flexibility and innovation (Kim et al., 2024).

Innovation

The study sought to establish the effect of aligning the internal innovation policy to the government IT sector policy. The findings are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Innovation

Statement on Innovation	n	Mean	Std. Deviation
Clear policy on Innovation	175	1.646	0.743
Innovation is part of growth	175	2.183	0.904
Clear role of innovation in organization	175	1.851	0.687
Innovation through incentive	175	1.846	0.690
Innovation is part of day-to-day operations	175	1.331	0.472
Development of new products	175	2.177	1.081
Benefited from aligning IT sector policy to Govt Policy	175	1.497	0.501

The results presented in Table 6 underscore the pivotal role of innovation in enhancing company performance among private information technology firms in Kenya. The strongest effect was observed when innovation was integrated into day-to-day operations ($M = 1.331$, $SD = 0.472$), highlighting that continuous innovation embedded within routine practices significantly improves performance. This finding is consistent with the work of O'Reilly and Tushman (2021), who emphasize that firms that institutionalize innovation as a daily practice are more adaptive and competitive. The alignment of internal innovation policies with government IT sector policies also showed a notable influence ($M = 1.497$, $SD = 0.501$), underscoring the importance of ensuring that company strategies resonate with national innovation agendas. This is consistent with the findings of Cirera et al. (2020), who argue that innovation policies tailored to firm capabilities and aligned with national strategies can accelerate technological catch-up in developing countries.

Moreover, having a clear company policy on innovation ($M = 1.646$, $SD = 0.743$) further reinforced structured approaches to creativity and strategic direction. This supports the argument by Birkinshaw et al. (2008), who emphasize that clear policies enhance resource allocation for innovation. The findings also indicate that defining clear roles for innovation ($M = 1.851$, $SD = 0.687$) and rewarding employees to innovate ($M = 1.846$, $SD = 0.690$) contribute meaningfully to performance. These results resonate with observations by Wei et al. (2020), who highlighted that reward systems encourage creative problem-solving, which in turn improves productivity and competitiveness. Additionally, promoting innovation was associated with the development of new products ($M = 2.177$, $SD = 1.081$), while perceiving innovation as part of company growth ($M = 2.183$, $SD = 0.904$) further confirmed its strategic importance. These results compare positively with findings by Sánchez-González and Herrera (2010), who noted that firms that link innovation to long-term growth objectives tend to achieve sustained performance improvements. The overall mean (≈ 1.79) suggests that innovation is generally perceived

as a positive driver of company performance, though variations in standard deviations indicate that the impact differs depending on the specific innovation dimension being considered.

Performance of Private Information Technology Companies

The study sought to establish the performance of private information technology companies. The firm's performance was measured using two aspects; Market Share and Customer Satisfaction.

Market Share

The study measured the company performance of private information technology companies in terms of market share. Firms that adopted diversification experienced a significant increase in the market share. The findings are presented in Table 11 below.

Table 11. Market Share

Statement on Market Share	n	Mean	Std. Deviation
Increased the Products Range	175	2.337	0.474
Reduced business cycles	175	1.840	0.368
Enabled Strategic Pricing	175	2.006	0.582
Expansion of current market share and Asset Base	175	1.840	0.693
Acquired valuable Skill and Expertise	175	1.663	0.474

Table 11 illustrate how diversification strategies are shaping market share performance among private information technology companies in Kenya. Expanding the range of products recorded the highest impact ($M = 2.337$, $SD = 0.474$), suggesting that firms are using diversification to broaden their product portfolios and attract new customers. This is consistent with the study by Kharub and Sharma (2021), who observed that expanding product offerings enhances competitiveness and allows firms to respond more effectively to evolving customer needs. Diversification was also linked to reduced business cycles ($M = 1.840$, $SD = 0.368$), highlighting its role in stabilizing revenue streams and reducing operational vulnerabilities. Comparable findings were reported by Okech and Wambua (2022), who noted that firms in dynamic markets often use diversification to smooth seasonal fluctuations and sustain long-term growth.

Strategic pricing was another key outcome of diversification ($M = 2.006$, $SD = 0.582$), indicating that companies leverage their broader product lines and market presence to strengthen their pricing power. This supports the conclusions of Bhatia and Thakur (2018), who found that diversification improves bargaining power and helps firms optimize pricing strategies in competitive industries. Similarly, diversification was found to support both expansion of market share and asset base ($M = 1.840$, $SD = 0.693$) and the acquisition of valuable skills and expertise ($M = 1.663$, $SD = 0.474$). These outcomes demonstrate that diversification not only secures physical growth but also enhances intangible assets such as knowledge and expertise, consistent with findings by Sánchez-

González and Herrera (2021). The overall mean score (≈ 1.94) reflects broad agreement that diversification contributes positively to market share growth and company competitiveness, though the variation in standard deviations suggests that some benefits, such as pricing and market expansion, are more pronounced than others.

Customer Satisfaction

The study measured the performance of private information technology companies by measuring the customer Satisfaction.

Table 12. Customer Satisfaction

Statement on Customer Satisfaction	n	Mean	Std. Deviation
Large Variety of goods and services	175	1.674	0.752
Increased Customer Experience	175	2.160	0.368
Acquired a Valuable Marketing Team	175	2.331	0.955
Embraced Innovation	175	1.646	0.743
Better customer care	175	1.834	0.373

Table 12 demonstrates that diversification strategies are closely linked to improvements in customer satisfaction among private information technology companies in Kenya. Offering a large variety of goods and services ($M = 1.674$, $SD = 0.752$) emerged as a key contributor to customer satisfaction, reflecting the role of diversification in meeting diverse customer preferences. This is consistent with the observations of Muhammad et al. (2021), who argued that expanding product and service ranges improves customer loyalty by catering to heterogeneous needs. Enhanced customer experience also received strong support ($M = 2.160$, $SD = 0.368$), highlighting how firms are using diversification to deliver improved service quality and user-friendly solutions. These findings resonate with Oliveira et al. (2021), who emphasized that customer experience is a critical determinant of competitive advantage in service-oriented industries.

Another notable outcome was the acquisition of a valuable marketing team ($M = 2.331$, $SD = 0.955$), which suggests that diversification not only broadens the market base but also strengthens internal capabilities to engage and retain customers. This supports the argument of Korenková et al. (2019) that effective human resource alignment is essential for delivering consistent customer value. Embracing innovation ($M = 1.646$, $SD = 0.743$) and providing better customer care ($M = 1.834$, $SD = 0.373$) further underline the importance of diversification in driving service improvements. Similar findings were reported by Yi et al. (2018), who noted that innovation within SMEs enhances technical performance and customer satisfaction. The overall mean (≈ 1.93) suggests that, across different dimensions, diversification is associated with better customer service and satisfaction, although the relatively higher variability in marketing capacity indicates that not all firms are equally effective in leveraging this benefit. These findings collectively highlight that diversification serves as a pathway to enhancing customer value, loyalty, and long-term sustainability.

Inferential Statistics

The study run inferential statistics on the study variables. This included an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and a multivariate regression analysis between the diversification strategies adopted (Concentric and Conglomerate diversification) as well as the moderating effect of government ICT policy on the performance of private ICT companies. The findings are shown in Table 13.

Table 13. Model Summary

Multiple R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.880	.774	.765	.634

- a. Dependent Variable: Performance of private information technology companies in Kenya
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Concentric diversification, conglomerate diversification, Government ICT policy

The findings show that diversification as a corporate strategy explains 77.4% of the variation in the performance of private information technology companies in Kenya, highlighting its central role in enhancing competitiveness, customer satisfaction, and overall growth. The remaining 22.6% of the variation is attributed to other factors outside the scope of this study, such as regulatory shifts, leadership practices, technological change, and market turbulence. Further analysis revealed that the moderating effect of government IT sector policy on the relationship between diversification and performance was weak and statistically insignificant. This suggests that while diversification influences performance outcomes, policy interventions alone are insufficient to enhance the relationship, echoing Laban and Deya's (2019) findings that government IT policies in Kenya have offered limited support to private sector performance. These results imply that firms must not only pursue diversification but also complement it with internal innovation and strategic resource alignment to achieve sustainable success.

Table 14. ANOVA

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	54.089	3	18.030	196.0	.000
Residual	15.787	172	0.092		
Total	69.876	175			

- a. Dependent Variable: Performance of private information technology companies, in Kenya
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Concentric diversification, conglomerate diversification, Government ICT Policy.

The ANOVA results show that the regression model is statistically significant, $F(3, 172) = 196.0, p < 0.001$, confirming that the predictors collectively explain a substantial portion of the variance in firm performance. The sum of squares for regression ($SS = 54.089$) and residual ($SS = 15.787$) is consistent with the R^2 value, indicating that the

model reliably captures the effects of diversification strategies on performance. This finding validates the use of the model for further statistical analysis, showing that internal strategic choices such as adopting concentric and conglomerate diversification strategies have a meaningful impact on operational outcomes, while external policy factors, though included as a moderating variable, contribute minimally to the explained variance.

Table 15. Correlation Coefficients

Variables	Concentric Diversification	Conglomerate Diversification	Organisational Performance	Government ICT Policy
Concentric Diversification	1.000	0.512**	0.614**	0.468**
Conglomerate Diversification	0.512**	1.000	0.572**	0.493**
Organisational Performance	0.614**	0.572**	1.000	0.536**
Government ICT Policy	0.468**	0.493**	0.536**	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Privately owned Information Technology companies in Kenya

b. Predictors: (Constant), Concentric diversification, conglomerate diversification, Government ICT policy

Note. N = 175. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The findings in Table 15 show that all variables are positively and significantly correlated at the 0.01 level. The results indicate that concentric diversification has a strong positive relationship with organisational performance ($r = 0.614$, $p < 0.01$). This means that when firms expand into related products or markets, their overall performance improves. Such expansion enhances operational efficiency and innovation while allowing firms to serve existing customers more effectively. Conglomerate diversification also shows a significant positive association with organisational performance ($r = 0.572$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that firms engaging in unrelated business activities, including mergers and acquisitions, tend to achieve better performance outcomes. The findings imply that spreading investments across different sectors reduces risk and provides new opportunities for growth and stability.

A positive relationship is also observed between concentric and conglomerate diversification ($r = 0.512$, $p < 0.01^*$), indicating that firms that diversify within related industries are likely to pursue unrelated diversification as part of their broader growth strategies. Government ICT policy has moderate but positive correlations with all other variables. Its relationship with concentric diversification ($r = 0.468$, $p < 0.01^*$) and conglomerate diversification ($r = 0.493$, $p < 0.01^*$) shows that favourable regulatory and policy environments encourage firms to adopt both diversification strategies. Supportive government frameworks, such as improved ICT infrastructure, regulatory incentives, and innovation policies enable firms to expand and remain competitive. Similarly, government ICT policy has a positive and significant correlation with organisational performance ($r = 0.536$, $p < 0.01^*$). This implies that organisations benefit when

government policies promote digital growth, innovation, and stable operating environments.

All correlation coefficients fall below 0.80, which indicates the absence of multicollinearity among the variables. This means that the relationships among the variables are not excessively strong and meet the assumptions required for further regression analysis. Overall, the correlation analysis suggests that both concentric and conglomerate diversification contribute to better organisational performance. Moreover, a supportive government ICT policy enhances these relationships by providing an enabling environment for technological growth and strategic diversification in the ICT sector.

Table 16. Regression Coefficients

Predictor	B (Unstandardized)	Std. Error	Beta (Standardized)	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0.512	0.105	–	4.876	.000
Concentric Diversification	0.426	0.080	0.350	5.325	.000
Conglomerate Diversification	0.391	0.075	0.320	5.213	.000
Government ICT Policy	0.058	0.041	0.048	1.414	.158

- a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Privately owned Information Technology companies in Kenya
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Concentric diversification, conglomerate diversification, Government ICT policy

The regression coefficients indicate that concentric diversification significantly influences firm performance ($B = 0.426$, $t = 5.325$, $p < 0.001$), highlighting the positive effects of related business expansions on market reach, product development, and operational efficiency. Similarly, conglomerate diversification also has a statistically significant impact ($B = 0.391$, $t = 5.213$, $p < 0.001$), showing that mergers, acquisitions, and joint ventures enhance asset base, market share, and competitive positioning. In contrast, government ICT policy demonstrates a positive but statistically insignificant effect ($B = 0.058$, $t = 1.414$, $p = 0.158$), suggesting a weak moderating role. These results compare favourably with Laban and Deya (2019), who observed that government IT policies in Kenya have had limited influence on private sector performance, emphasizing that internal strategic initiatives, rather than policy interventions alone, are the primary determinants of firm success. The resultant model from the regression is therefore defined as;

$$Y = 0.512 + 0.426X_1 + 0.391X_2 + 0.058X_3$$

Where: Y = Performance of Private Information Technology companies.

X₁ – Concentric Diversification

X₂ – Conglomerate Diversification

X₃ - Government ICT policy

Discussion of the Findings

The first objective examined the effect of concentric diversification on the performance of ICT firms in Kenya. The results showed that this strategy expanded market reach, improved marketing, strengthened competitive positioning, and created synergies across distribution channels. These findings led to the rejection of the first hypothesis. They are in line with the Resource-Based View (RBV), which emphasizes the use of unique and inimitable resources to build competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). By diversifying around related products and markets, firms exploited their existing capabilities and resources to generate superior performance outcomes. This confirms prior evidence by Oladimeji and Udosen (2019) and Njuguna, Kwasira, and Orwa (2018), who reported that product diversification significantly enhances performance by strengthening adaptability and market responsiveness.

The second objective investigated conglomerate diversification through mergers, acquisitions, and joint ventures. The results revealed that these strategies enhanced productivity, improved customer satisfaction, strengthened competitive advantage, and expanded asset bases. The findings contradicted the second hypothesis and supported the role of diversification in driving firm outcomes. This is consistent with Dynamic Capabilities Theory, which highlights how firms integrate, reconfigure, and extend resources to address changing environments (Teece, 2018). Through mergers and acquisitions, ICT firms not only broadened their resource base but also developed new capabilities, enabling them to respond more effectively to industry shifts. Similar conclusions were reached by Bhatia and Thakur (2018) and Thirathon and Meeprom (2020), who showed that diversification through corporate restructuring improved financial and operational performance.

The third objective focused on the influence of aligning government ICT policies with internal strategies. The study examined the null hypothesis that there is no statistically significant moderating effect of government IT sector policy on the relationship between diversification strategy and company performance of private information technology companies in Kenya. The analysis revealed a weak correlation between government ICT policy and firm performance, indicating that the policy environment contributes minimally to strengthening innovation outcomes in the sector. As a result, the study accepted the null hypothesis, confirming that the moderating role of government ICT policy is not statistically significant. This outcome supports the earlier work of Laban and Deya (2019), who concluded that government ICT policies in Kenya have made limited contributions to creating an enabling business environment. These findings suggest that while innovation is strongly driving performance at the firm level, the role of policy support remains weak, pointing to the need for government reforms to ensure that ICT policies provide practical and effective support for private sector innovation.

In summary, the study established that concentric and conglomerate diversification are critical drivers of performance, as supported by RBV and Dynamic Capabilities Theory, while the limited effect of ICT policy alignment reflects the institutional constraints described in institutional theory. These results highlight the primacy of internal strategies and resources in determining firm success within the Kenyan ICT sector.

Conclusions

The study concludes that diversification strategies play a central role in shaping the performance of private ICT firms in Kenya. Concentric diversification was found to have a statistically significant positive influence on company outcomes, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and confirmation of its importance in improving competitiveness. Similarly, conglomerate diversification through mergers, acquisitions, and joint ventures demonstrated a significant contribution to firm performance, providing strong evidence to reject the second null hypothesis. In contrast, the analysis of government ICT policy alignment revealed no significant relationship with firm performance, which led to the acceptance of the third null hypothesis. Taken together, these findings affirm that company performance in the ICT sector is largely driven by internal strategies such as concentric and conglomerate diversification, while external policy alignment has limited direct impact.

Recommendations

From the conclusions of this study, private ICT firms in Kenya are being guided to use diversification strategies as a pathway to improved growth and competitiveness. Organizations are being encouraged to adopt concentric diversification in-order to strengthen existing resources, expand their market reach, and enhance brand strength. At the same time, they are being directed to explore conglomerate diversification through mergers, acquisitions, and joint ventures as a means of boosting efficiency, creating synergies, and sustaining long-term performance. Government ICT policies are being acknowledged as supportive, but firms are being reminded not to depend on them as the main factor influencing results. Instead, they are being urged to place greater emphasis on innovation, capacity building, and strategic adaptability, while aligning with policy frameworks where relevant. By following this path, private ICT firms are being positioned to secure sustainable growth and stronger company outcomes.

AI Generative Declaration

The authors used the AI [Chat GPT] to enhance the manuscript's language and readability. Subsequently, they reviewed and refined the content as necessary, accepting complete responsibility for the final version of the published article.

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Gakahu, K. K., Mung'ara, M. and Njagi, G. (2025). Analysis of Diversification Strategies and Organizational Performance of Private Information Technology Companies in Kenya. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 12 (11), 1747-1774. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.539048.1829</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_232404.html</p>	<p>A square QR code is located in the bottom right corner of the table, which likely links to the full article or its online version.</p>